
Clips from the History of Construction and Activity of Tuyatortar Canal

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Abstract: This article presents information about the Tuyatortar canal, its construction and history of operation, which has gained significant importance in the history of irrigation of the Jizzakh oasis. The Tuyatortar canal is a water structure that has been in operation since the middle of ancient times and has contributed enough to the development of irrigated agriculture in the existing countries.

Key words: Jizzakh oasis, irrigated farming, Tuyatortar canal, Zarafshan river, Yakhya Gulomov, Abdulakhad Mukhammadjanov, Timurid period, Abdullaxan II period, Abdullanama, Mirzo Bade Devon.

INTRODUCTION

It is recognized in historical sources that in the Middle Ages the inhabitants of our country were mainly engaged in agriculture, animal husbandry, crafts and trade. In the states that functioned during this period, the inhabitants of the cities were mainly engaged in crafts and trade, but agriculture was not a foreign field for them either. In the villages, they were engaged not only in agriculture, but also in animal husbandry. In this regard, the city of Jizzakh and its oasis are no exception. Nevertheless, a type of sedentary agriculture based on artificial irrigation systems has been formed and occupied an important place in the way of life of the inhabitants of the oasis since ancient times. From the beginning of the Middle Ages, a large number of farms based on irrigated agriculture based on water sources such as Sangzar, Zominsuv, Shakhristsansay, and Syrdarya appeared in this region from Gallaaral to Khojand, which is called the country of Ustrushana according to the current territorial concept.

Although the history of irrigation of Jizzakh oasis starts from very ancient times, its research process is small. According to archaeologists who partially studied the irrigation history of Jizzakh, there are a number of artificial irrigation canals in the oasis. The most difficult of these artificial canals is the Tuyatortar canal, which originates from the ancient Zarafshan river.

MAIN PART

About the Tuyatortar canal, academician Yakhya Gulomov said, “We, experts working on the history of irrigation, have never seen such a labor-intensive, low-water, and self-flowing canal as the Tuyatortar canal among the artificial canals in Central Asia” he said[Gulomov, 1962, 1963].

Academician Abdulakhad Mukhammadjanov in his book “History of Irrigation of the Lower Zarafshan Valley” analyzes that the water of the Zarafshan River even reached the Jizzakh oasis through the Tuyatortar canal, and due to this, the amount of irrigated agricultural land in the oasis increased dramatically in the last middle ages[Mukhammadjanov, 1972, p.128-129].

The Tuyatortar canal is still the main water source of the Jizzakh oasis, its length is 97 km. The Tuyatortar canal supplies water to the Bulungur steppes and the Gallaaral massif and the Jizzakh oasis through the Zarafshan river.

There is unclear information about when the Tuyatortar channel was created. Preliminary information about the Tuyatortar channel was recorded in Khafiz Tanish's work "Abdullanama". According to it, the construction of the Tuyatortar canal was rebuilt and repaired by Abdullah Khan. According to Y. Gulamov, a scholar of the history of ancient irrigated agriculture, in order to determine the time of construction of the canals that irrigated the agricultural lands, he studied the historical monuments around this canal and the irrigation networks preserved around the historical monuments. It is said that it is possible to come to an opinion on this basis after determining its location.

Therefore, in 1994, the Jizzakh archeological detachment conducted archaeological research around the Zarafshan oasis and the Tuyatortar canal. The main purpose of conducting research is to determine when the canal was built based on the monuments preserved around the Tuyatortar canal, which originates from the Zarafshan river. The first studies in this regard were also studied.

G. Alimov, who conducted preliminary research on the Tuyatortar canal, reports that the waters of the old Tuyatortar Shah Stream reached Mirzachol. There is a Farmantepa monument 4-5 kilometers northeast of the Ravothoja dam of the Zarafshan river. The monument is located on the right side of the Tuyatortar canal. It is noted that the main part of the canal was built in the 5th-7th centuries as a result of the archaeologist S. Anarbaev's research, and that the canal was abandoned by the end of the 7th century [Anarbaev, 1974, p.54].

Further studies completely deny this. Because the archaeological material evidences found date back to the beginning of our era. In the course of the research, ceramics belonging to the early Kushan period were collected from the tomb of Togaysufi and other mounds in the small oasis called Dusmat around the canal. In the lower part of this small oasis, materials from the Kushan period were not found. This certainly confirms that the Dosmat oasis operated at the expense of the Tuyatortar channel. At the place where Tuyatortar canal flows through the village of Tazarruk, that is, on the right side of the canal, the Tortkultepa monument was also noted [Pardaev, Suyunov, 1994, p.50-52].

The archaeological finds from this monument indicate that the monument was operated from the 10th-12th centuries due to the Tuyatortar canal. Because a small tributary of the Tuyatortar canal, which goes around Tortkultepa, is still preserved. The Tuyatortar canal, which is the main water source of the Jizzakh oasis, was completely destroyed during the Mongol invasion. Finally, it was renovated and restored during the reign of Amir Temur and the Timurids. At the beginning of the 15th century, in the Jizzakh oasis, they began to gradually restore agriculture, including artificial irrigation networks, which are considered its basis.

The results of the research show that the Tuyatortar canal was restored during the Timurid era. For example, archaeological findings from the ruins of Kurgantepa in Gallaaral and the surrounding monuments, as well as material evidence from the Timurid period from the ruins of Kaliyatepa in Jizzakh district, as well as information from the ruins of Orda in this oasis during this period. It can also be seen from the fact that the irrigation canals have been restored. But after the death of Ulugbek (1449), the struggle for the throne began, and the country's economy became somewhat depressed. Along with many irrigation networks and artificial irrigation facilities, the Tuyatortar canal will also fail.

A century later, in the second half of the 16th century, in the Khanate of Bukhara, on the one hand, the strengthening of the political position of the central government, and on the other hand, the increase in the demand for fertile land with the increase in the process of migration of Uzbek clans to settled farming life, led to the expansion of irrigation works in the country to release water to idle lands and develop new lands. The oasis of Jizzakh was not left out of such creativity. According to the accuracy of archaeological data and historical sources, in the second half of the 16th century, in the Bukhara Khanate, especially in its central part, in the Zarafshan Valley, a number of large irrigation facilities were built and restored [Tanish Bukhari, 1969, p.361].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In regulating the distribution of water of the Zarafshan River, water gauges and water dividing bridges such as “Puli Mekhtar Kasim”, “Puli Charminar” and “Puli Jandar” built on the Zarafshan River in 1582 were especially important[Mukhammadjanov,1974, p.56].

According to the historical sources of the end of the 18th century, Mirzo Bade Devon’s work entitled “Majma' al-arkom”, the water of the Zarafshan river was distributed to irrigation systems through these structures. One of these irrigation systems, the opening of the Tuyatortar canal, was one of the major irrigation constructions of the Jizzakh oasis water supply carried out at that time.

Bukhara Khan Abdulla Khan II in order to keep the strategically important city of Jizzakh in his hands (1556-1598) involved the people and re-excavated the main part of the Tuyatortar canal, and re-dug the middle and lower parts. The water of the Zarafshan River passes through the Tuyatortar canal through the villages of Farmantepa, Dosmat, Taypaksoy, Shorbulak, Muzbel, Tozarruk and flows into Sangzar near the village of Gul. It provides water to Jizzakh oasis through Sangzar. Even now, the Tuyatortar canal is dug along its ancient course. During the period of Abdulla Khan II, the canal was the first to flow approximately 4-6 m per second. a cubic meter of water has flowed. In the second half of the 16th century, 10,000 acres of land were developed in the oasis through the Tuyatortar canal to was close[Suyunov, 1999, p.29-30].

CONCLUSION

On the basis of the archaeological materials obtained in this way and based on historical sources, the following conclusions can be drawn. Based on the physical evidence found at the Farmantepa monument, it can be concluded that the main part of the Tuyatortar canal was built at the beginning of our era. In addition, the materials taken from around the Tuyatortar canal provide information about the destruction of the Tuyatortar canal during the Arab period and its restoration in the 10th-11th centuries. The irrigation network preserved around the monument of Tortkoltepa originates from the Tuyatortar canal. After a certain time, the ancient Tuyatortar canal, which is considered a unique water structure of the Jizzakh oasis, was built by Bukhara Khan Abdullakhan II from Bulungur steppes to Sangzar, and it is still functioning.

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